

Toward an intelligent and safe transportation infrastructure: the SmartRail project

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Abstract—In this work, we introduce the SmartRail, a system of embedded arrays of fiber optics sensors for the continuous monitoring of the track geometry. We discuss how our embedded technology allows early detection of even short-wave defects while overcoming the robustness concerns of the SoA. The metrological principle is formulated based on an analytical/FE model, and experimental tests validated the operation of the system with excellent agreement with the theoretical predictions.

I. INTRODUCTION

NOWADAYS, modern railway infrastructures ensure a high standard of quality in terms of track geometry according to European standards [1], [2]. Still, safe and continuous operation of the railway are exposed to local and distributed collapses due to extreme weather events and anomalous geophysical landslides. Hence a current challenge is to conceive an intelligent railway infrastructure based on a real-time interrogation in which critical conditions can be detected at an early stage.

At the State of the Art, several technologies have been proposed to embed sensors within the railway [3]–[7], mainly adopting arrays of fiber optic sensors [3], [8]. Experimental validations [8] demonstrated the possibility of correlating the measured signals with the local deformation or *strain* of the rail, mitigating the spurious effects due to the strain-temperature cross-sensitivity. However, real applicability of these prototypes requires optimization and improved robustness to protect the sensors from an extremely harsh environment.

In this work, we introduce the concept of the SmartRail, an innovative system based on embedded arrays of fiber optic sensors for the continuous monitoring of the track geometry. The layout of the system, shown in Fig. 1, endorses equally-spaced metallic patches brazed to each rail. In this way, the sensors can be embedded into the patch and being protected.

We first discuss the metrological principle, i.e. how to correlate the array of measured patch-strain to the geometry of the track. To this purpose a local analytical/FE model is formulated to compute the local curvatures of the rail in the vertical and horizontal plane. Reconstruction of the geometry relies on a global model, exploiting the differential relationship between the curvatures and the displacement of the rail beam. The choice of spatial resolution is also addressed through simulations to find a trade-off value between cost

Fig. 1. Layout scheme of the SmartRail. b) detail of the assembly rail-sensitized patch; c) reference positions of the FBGs (left rail).

and detection accuracy when sampling short-wave defects. Finally, we discuss a laboratory validation to demonstrate the effectiveness of a prototype in estimating controlled rail deformation with low levels of noise.

II. PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION

The schematic of the local model is shown in Fig. 2 where the 3D deformation of a SmartRail section is projected on two auxiliary planes - horizontal and vertical - where only pure bending exists. Hence the overall strain measured by the FBG sensors ε^A and ε^B is determined by the superposition of the strain due to the horizontal bending, $\varepsilon_y^A, \varepsilon_y^B$ and vertical bending $\varepsilon_z^A, \varepsilon_z^B$.

At this point, we introduce a strain transmission function to correlate the strain of the patch $\varepsilon_A, \varepsilon_B$ to the correspondent strain of the rail e_A and e_B . This function must be evaluated for both points *A* and *B*, and for both bending planes. To this end, we adopted a FE model to estimate the strain fields of the patch and the rail during simultaneous imposed deformation. Consequently, given the measured strains, one obtains the following expression for the curvatures:

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma &= \frac{1}{y_A} \frac{\tau_z^B \varepsilon^A + k \tau_z^A \varepsilon^B}{\tau_y (\tau_z^B + k \tau_z^A)} \\ \rho &= \frac{1}{z_A} \frac{k (\varepsilon^A - \varepsilon^B)}{\tau_z^B + k \tau_z^A} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Note that by k we indicate the ratio z_A/z_B .

Given the vectors of estimated curvatures, the geometry of the rail is reconstructed through a global model, relying on the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory. Accordingly, the alignment v and the longitudinal level w are computed by double-integration of the curvatures γ and ρ .

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Fig. 2. Schematic of the local model allowing correlation of the measured strains (FBG on the patch) and the strains of the rail through the definition of four strain transmission factors.

Fig. 3. Effect of the spatial resolution on the detection of an early defect (sampled at the reference value of 0.5 m).

Due to discretization, care must be taken in the choice of the spatial resolution Δ , which introduces an error between the estimated displacements and the real geometrical profiles. To this end, we performed simulations to study the effects of increasing the spatial resolution. The model, in Fig. 3, takes as input the original profiles (solid lines) sampled at 0.5 m. The corresponding strains on the patch are decimated for three values of $\Delta = 1.2, 2.4, 3.6$ m, to reconstruct the under-sampled profiles (dotted lines). Despite a residual error, the early defect - alignment surpassing the threshold - is clearly detected only for $\Delta = 1.2$ m, while higher values of the resolution are prone to false negatives.

III. PRELIMINARY EXPERIMENT AND CONCLUSIONS

An experimental setup was arranged to validate a first prototype of the SmartRail. Controlled deformation is achieved as in Fig. 4 by a three points bending test, performed for stepped values of a static load, generated by a hydraulic

Fig. 4. Experimental setup arranged for the validation of a SmartRail prototype on a rail beam of 6 m with three patches (6 embedded FBGs).

actuator in the interval 5:5:50 kN. Besides, strain gauges were welded on the rear side of the rail at the same coordinates of the FBGs so that they are subjected to the same rail deformation.

In this way, it was possible to estimate an experimental strain transmission factor as the ratio of the strain measured by the FBG and by the strain gauge. Results are in good agreement with the theory, with an error around 5%. Besides, the signal-to-noise-ratio of the FBG reveals higher than the strain gauges for all the values of the load.

In the future, we aim to execute field test on a track length of 60 m to evaluate the damage detection performance of the system and the achievable confidence level.

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